

Synthesis of 3-aryl-2,6-diphenylimino-4-(*S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl)-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides

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Abstract : A series of 3-aryl-2,6-diphenylimino-4-(*S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl)-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines (hydrochlorides) have been synthesized by the reaction of *S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl-1-aryl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (1) with phenyl isocyanodichloride (2). The compounds were characterized by IR, NMR and mass spectral analysis.

Keywords : Lactosyl isodithiobiurets, phenyl isocyanodichloride(II), lactosyl thiadiazines.

S-Lactosyl compounds have wide applications in industries, medicinal chemistry and in many other ways¹. With this end in view, an attempt has been made to synthesize some sulphur linked lactosyl compounds. In continuation of our recent work in the chemistry of lactosyl thioureides and their analogs², we wish to report herein the synthesis of 3-aryl-2,6-diphenylimino-4-(*S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl)-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines as hydrochlorides (Scheme 1).

where, R = (a) phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *m*-tolyl, (g) *p*-tolyl

Ac = COCH₃ (acetyl)

Ph = C₆H₅ (phenyl)

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

Condensation of *S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (2.2 g, 0.0025 mol) with phenyl isocyanodichloride (0.4 g, 0.0025 mol) in chloroform (30 ml) was carried out for 2.5 h. The evolution of hydrogen chloride was noticed. The excess of chloroform was distilled off. The resultant viscous residue was triturated

several times with petroleum ether (60–80°) to furnish a granular solid (3a). It was purified with ethanol-water. It gave charring test and was non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. It was found to be optically active⁷.

The IR, NMR³ and mass⁵ spectral analyses clearly indicated the product as 3-phenyl-2,6-diphenylimino-4-(*S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl)-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochloride (3a).

When the interaction of phenyl isocyanodichloride was extended to other *S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl-1,5-disubstituted-2,4-isodithiobiurets corresponding title compounds (3b-g) were isolated.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on electrothermal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra of the compounds were recorded on KBr on a FT IR Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were run on Bruker DRX-300 instrument using CDCl₃ solution with TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on Jeol SX-102 FAB instrument. Specific rotations were recorded on digital polarimeter.

The required *S*-hepta-*O*-acetyl lactosyl-1,5-disubstituted-2,4-isodithiobiurets² and phenyl isocyanodichloride⁶ were prepared by known procedure.

3a : Yield 75%, m.p. 175–177 °C, [α]_D³³ –312.7° (c, 0.973, CHCl₃), IR (cm⁻¹) 2982 (Ar-H), 1750 (C=O), 1597 (S-C=N), 1493, 1443, 1231, 1054, 757; ¹H NMR δ 7.6–7.2 (15H, m, aromatic), 5.3–3.8 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2.1–1.9 ppm (21H, m, 7COCH₃); MS (*m/z*) 1042

(M⁺), 619, 331, 229, 169, 127, 109 (Found : C, 54.01; H, 4.89; N, 5.45; S, 6.19. Calcd. for C₄₇H₅₀O₁₇N₄S₂.HCl : C, 54.13; H, 4.80; N, 5.37; S, 6.14%).

3b : Yield 68%, m.p. 150–151 °C, [α]_D³³ 31.2° (c, 0.960, CHCl₃) (Found : C, 52.51; H, 4.64; N, 5.31; S, 5.99. Calcd. for C₄₇H₄₉O₁₇N₄S₂Cl.HCl : C, 52.41; H, 4.55; N, 5.20; S, 5.94%).

3c : Yield 76%, m.p. 170–172 °C, [α]_D³³ 111.5° (c, 0.986, CHCl₃) (Found : C, 52.53; H, 4.64; N, 5.29; S, 5.84. Calcd. for C₄₇H₄₉O₁₇N₄S₂Cl.HCl : C, 52.41; H, 4.55; N, 5.20; S, 5.94%).

3d : Yield 84%, m.p. 161–162 °C, [α]_D³³ -50.3° (c, 0.993, CHCl₃); IR (cm⁻¹) 2974 (Ar-H), 1749 (C=O), 1598 (S-C=N), 1542, 1442, 1231, 1054, 757; ¹H NMR δ 7.3–6.9 (14H, m, aromatic), 5.3–3.8 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2.1–1.9 ppm (21H, m, 7COCH₃); MS (*m/z*) 1076 (M⁺), 619, 331, 229, 169, 127, 109 (Found : C, 52.57; H, 4.59; N, 5.32; S, 5.86. Calcd. for C₄₇H₄₉O₁₇N₄S₂Cl.HCl : C, 52.41; H, 4.55; N, 5.20; S, 5.94%).

3e : Yield 96%, m.p. 158–160 °C, [α]_D³³ -57.30° (c, 1.046, CHCl₃) (Found : C, 54.67; H, 4.99; N, 5.42; S, 6.18. Calcd. for C₄₈H₅₂O₁₇N₄S₂.HCl : C, 54.54; H, 4.92; N, 5.30; S, 6.06%).

3f : Yield 99%, m.p. 163–164 °C, [α]_D³³ 30.1° (c, 0.966, CHCl₃) (Found : C, 54.64; H, 4.81; N, 5.39; S, 6.19. Calcd. for C₄₈H₅₂O₁₇N₄S₂.HCl : C, 54.54; H, 4.92; N, 5.30; S, 6.06%).

3g : Yield 92%, m.p. 182–184 °C, [α]_D³³ 197.9° (c, 0.960, CHCl₃); IR (cm⁻¹) 2928 (Ar-H), 1749 (C=O), 1596 (S-C=N), 1512, 1444, 1230, 1052, 757; ¹H NMR δ 7.6–6.9 (15H, m, aromatic), 5.3–3.8 (14H, m, lactose unit), 2–1.9 (21H, m, 7COCH₃); MS (*m/z*) 1056 (M⁺), 619, 559, 331, 229, 169, 127, 109 (Found : C, 54.61; H, 4.88; N, 5.36; S, 6.16. Calcd. for C₄₈H₅₂O₁₇N₄S₂.HCl : C, 54.54; H, 4.92; N, 5.30; S, 6.06%).

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